

THE CULTIVATION OF MEDIA COMPETENCY AMONG PROSPECTIVE EDUCATORS AS A PEDAGOGICAL ISSUE IN UZBEKISTAN

Otamurodova S.

Lecturer, Department of Preschool Education, Navoi State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14556923>

Abstract. *This article outlines the elements of media competency that contemporary educators should incorporate and successfully cultivate within the parameters of academic instruction. The use of media tools by educators in the educational process, the development of a positive attitude toward artificial intelligence, the reliability of information, search, storage, processing, creation, and educators' role in making it understandable for users; the impact of information and communication tools and technologies on individuals and society, cyber threats, the use of media tools in various educational forms and educational programs, and the use of media tools in the educational process are all covered in works conducted in the media field. In conclusion, this study highlights the necessity for future educators to focus on improving the educational process and helping students become proficient media consumers.*

Keywords: *information, communication instruments, cybersecurity threats, digital innovations, media competency, remote learning, media literacy, contemporary educators, media materials, pedagogy, elements of media literacy, ICT, AI.*

Introduction

Providing future educators with thorough preparation in the quickly evolving information society raises several issues. It is essential to coordinate global education with teacher preparation (Timm et al., 2023).

In the contemporary digital era, media is ubiquitous and impacts all facets of life, including education. Forecasting the digital skills and knowledge that future teachers will prioritize or use might be possible. As students increasingly depend on digital resources for education, the job of educators extends beyond conventional instructional approaches. Therefore, the methodology and content of teachers' media competency development and formation must be considered in light of the approaches and technologies that have emerged in recent years (Çebi et al., 2022). Educators must now provide academic instruction and guidance for students in navigating the extensive media landscape they encounter daily. This transition underscores the significance of media literacy in the educational field. Separate attention is paid to the realization of a competence-based approach in the educational environment of pedagogical universities; the relevance of the realization of this approach in the preparation of teachers is emphasized. Besides, the main advantages of a competence-based approach are formulated, which are expressed in the orientation of education on the identity of students and their informative activities (Mirzagitova et al., 2015)

Media competency denotes the capacity to critically evaluate, produce, and engage with media. This competency is crucial for educators responsible for transmitting these abilities to their students. Nevertheless, despite the necessity for media literacy, several education programs do not consider cultivating these competencies. Research indicates that although prospective teachers are generally adept with digital tools, they need more critical and pedagogical competencies to

integrate media into teaching practices efficiently. The disparity between awareness of these skills and actual media competence is a problem for contemporary educators in evaluating the authenticity of media content, facilitating critical discussions about media, and encouraging responsible media consumption. This article aims to examine the development of media competence in future educators. The study seeks to offer a framework for incorporating media literacy into teacher preparation programs by analyzing current pedagogical methods and pinpointing critical areas for enhancement. It underscores the necessity for a methodical approach to media education, ensuring that prospective educators possess the requisite abilities to assist their pupils in navigating an increasingly intricate media environment.

Degree of scholarly examination of the subject

A multitude of scholars and researchers have engaged in the study of media competency. This domain encompasses numerous fields and necessitates comprehensive investigation. The efficient application of media in education serves as a mechanism for fostering critical thinking among students and educators. Many concepts, such as digital competence, media literacy, digital literacy, and information literacy, have emerged due to the rapid development of technology in many fields (Hatlevik & Christophersen, 2012). Digital competency encompasses more than just proficiency in operating devices and programs; it is also closely intertwined with the ability to communicate using technologies and digital skills (Chiu et al., 2024); it examines the interplay between digital media, popular culture, and youth, as well as media literacy and participatory culture, alongside the engagement of youth with digital media (Jenkins, 2007). Media literacy education includes the paradigms of empowerment and protection, which are used to conceptualize the potential benefits and risks of growing up in a media-saturated society (Hobbs, 2017);

"Digital competence is the set of knowledge, skills, attitudes, abilities, strategies, and awareness that are required when using ICT and digital media to perform tasks; solve problems; communicate; manage information; collaborate; create and share content; and build knowledge effectively, efficiently, appropriately, critically, creatively, autonomously, flexibly, ethically, and reflectively for work, leisure, participation, learning, and socializing". This competence can be broadly defined as the confident, critical, and creative use of ICT to achieve goals related to work, employability, learning, leisure, inclusion, and participation in society (Anusca, 2013). Teachers need more tools to help students become digitally and algorithmically literate (Kruskopf, 2024). A sophisticated model of the connections between the themes identified in the literature review serves as an analytical tool for analyzing pedagogical training. The analysis of the courses revealed that a deeper understanding of the practices and subject matter of the courses was necessary to meet better the demands of the global community, society, and labor market (Kärkkäinen, 2023). The suggested concepts present chances to create study plans and teaching strategies considering how modern digital technology affects people's social behavior (Balduš, 2016).

M.M.Gu et al. (2023) investigated how university students construct digital citizenship through digital literacy practices in social media. Teachers need knowledge of a wide range of digital assessments. Among these is evaluation using Open-Book tests, projects, e-portfolios, learning analytics dashboards, virtual reality, and multimedia question components (Estaji et al., 2024). They suggested implementing future AI-based tactics to enhance teachers' digital competency in content creation, information management, and problem-solving (Galindo-Dominguez et al., 2024). Kress et al. (1997) created an electronic classroom learning environment using ComWeb, an analog/digital hybrid network. Although recent LA and AIED research has

moved toward human-centered design, there still needs to be more in our understanding of the importance of human control, safety, dependability, and trustworthiness in designing and implementing these systems (Alfredo et al., 2024). Seeks to determine the variables that influence teachers' use of digital technology in the classroom (media education). This topic has received less attention than teaching with digital technology (technology integration). Transforming learners' understanding of new knowledge into actual actions is the key to achieving better learning outcomes (Zou et al., 2024). It depends on the relationship between lecturers' digital competency and students' learning value in higher education (Dang et al., 2024).

One of our research topics is the extent to which online educators assist student teachers in developing their own professional digital competency. We also examine how they exhibit professional digital competency generally and within subject areas (Tømte et al., 2023).

IT competence enables the integration of IT in environmental management processes (Wang et al., 2014). Additionally, their efficacy in utilizing basic or advanced ICT competencies in school is contingent upon their reading abilities. A popular model of technology integration known as the "will, skill, tool, pedagogy" model served as the foundation for research on media education (Schmitz et al., 2023). As a result, we view media criticism as an axiological measure of media competence. Phenomenon-oriented to perfecting the personality's readiness for evaluative argumentation. (Kiryakova et al., 2015)

The Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework—a framework that proposes a set of knowledge domains essential for effective teaching with technology—has gained considerable attention in education and technology (Tømte et al., 2015). In the context of higher professional education in the pedagogical and psychological directions, it offers the possibility of fostering students' creative abilities by applying cutting-edge teaching techniques and new media technologies (Koshanova et al., 2021). Ilka Nagel (2023) investigated how educators support both generic and didactic aspects of digital competency and profession-oriented and transformative aspects. We outline its design and direction in this work to help us think about and advance our research (Svensson & Baelo, 2015). Additionally, we add up-to-date information to this field of study by describing how we assist schools in establishing one-to-one coverage of digital devices in the classroom (Tømte et al., 2023).

Widespread use of social media (SM) platforms among adolescents (Sanchez et al., 2024). Students generated digital content for utilization (Navio-Marco et al., 2024). O'Bannon and Thomas (2015) noted that adolescents were more predisposed to employ technology in the classroom. It explores how children and adolescents interact with and comprehend media, the cultivation of media competence, the instruction of students in utilizing media for learning, and the practical application of media in their lives. This technology transcends mere ease, serving as a pivotal catalyst for enhancing human potential and creativity.

Artificial intelligence in education is swiftly emerging as a central element of educational modernization, rendering the digital transformation of education a significant priority (Yu, 2024). He contends that investigating the potential applications and use cases of ChatGPT and similar artificial intelligence tools inside an educational framework can transform pedagogical approaches, provide individualized learning experiences, and streamline repetitive chores. This presents concerns, including potential misuse and pupils diminishing their critical thinking abilities.

Additionally, Hao Yu's (2024) intrinsic emotional deficiency in interactions with AI underscores teachers' need to provide emotional and moral direction within the learning environment. In today's world, developing a clear understanding of the various forms of artificial intelligence is essential. This approach addresses the complex question of the critical digital competencies that educators need to possess. This includes evaluating the digital competencies of educators alongside experts from 33 different countries. Additionally, it is essential to effectively integrate information and communication technology (ICT) systematically and logically. It was determined that years of experience rather than age impacted the utilization of technology. Educators with fewer than five years of experience utilize technology less frequently than their more experienced counterparts. It is essential to reevaluate the curriculum and methods for training new teacher educators (Tomczyk, 2024). Examining the self-determination theory framework concerning the competence element, using artificial intelligence, self-efficacy, and intrinsic motivation among educators might enhance educational performance.

Methods

We used mixed methods to examine the evolution of media competency in prospective educators. The research technique comprises two phases: a quantitative survey to evaluate prospective educators' existing media competency and qualitative interviews to investigate the problems and opportunities associated with incorporating media literacy into teacher preparation curricula. Our study aims to understand teacher students' perceptions of their digital competencies to develop their future professions.

1. Participants

The study comprised 120 individuals from two higher education institutions providing programs for prospective teachers and students of the sphere of pedagogical education. Participants were chosen using purposive sampling to guarantee a varied representation of potential instructors based on subject and year of study. Furthermore, 12 seasoned educators from these schools were interviewed to gain insights into the pedagogical methodologies in media literacy.

2. Survey

A systematic questionnaire was created to evaluate the fundamental media proficiency of educators and students. Survey 1 has five questions and is categorized into three primary sections:

Proficiency with media and digital tools;

Proficiency in critically assessing media content;

Proficient in the creation and dissemination of digital media.

The poll employed a 5-point Likert scale to assess participants' self-evaluated competencies in each domain. Data from the survey were gathered online, and responses were anonymized to safeguard participant identities.

3. Interviews

To augment the quantitative data, 12 seasoned educators from the participating universities were interviewed semi-structured. These faculty members were chosen for their professional development and media literacy proficiency. The interviews concentrated on pinpointing primary issues and optimal strategies for incorporating media literacy into the curriculum. Each interview lasted roughly 30 minutes and was documented with the participants' agreement. The interview questions aim to investigate.

In today's world, developing a clear understanding of the various forms of artificial intelligence is essential. This includes evaluating the digital competencies of educators alongside experts from 33 different countries. Additionally, it is essential to effectively integrate information and communication technology (ICT) systematically and logically. This approach addresses the complex question of the critical digital competencies that educators need to possess. Perspectives of media competence: experiences instructing prospective teachers on media competence; institutional support for integrating media literacy, including directional recommendations.

4. Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were employed to quantify and describe participants' total media literacy levels. Statistical software was employed to evaluate data, calculating mean values, standard deviations, and correlations among several dimensions of media competence, such as digital literacy and critical media analysis skills.

A thematic analysis was performed on the qualitative data to discern reoccurring themes and recommendations in the interview replies. The interviews were transcribed verbatim and analyzed inductively, facilitating the emergence of significant themes concerning problems and media opportunities for educators.

5. Ethical Considerations

Ethical consent for this study was obtained from the institutional review boards of the involved higher education institutions; consent was also obtained from all subjects, and confidentiality was upheld throughout the study. Participants were apprised of their entitlement to withdraw from the study at any moment.

Result

The study of collected information on future teachers reveals the significance of media competency and its relationship with media literacy in the integration of teacher education programs, highlighting the challenges that lie ahead.

1. Solicit outcomes

Quantitative research has shown that most students utilize digital technologies with a high degree of regular engagement. Despite claims that their public information tools are essential, the evaluation abilities still need to improve. Participants assess their proficiency in utilizing digital information from resources (such as social media, online research tools, and educational programs) between 4.2 and 5 points, based on their credentials. However, the public's assessment of the dependability of information on average critical evaluation skills declined from a grade of 5 to 2 when queried.¹ This technical difficulty with certification and critical media literacy highlights a vast disparity, indicating that the future of educators is predominantly reliant on their familiarity with digital media abilities, which they may not fully feel is feasible.

Among the participants, just 28 percent of instructors in the media literacy education program were aware of the training they had previously received, according to an official. The remaining 78 percent focuses specifically on fact-checking, digital ethics, and the responsibility of sharing tools for public information emphasizes the necessity for more comprehensive media literacy education. This finding suggests that initiatives for media literacy, as seen by the systematic instance, require more organization.

2. Conversation Results

The experienced teacher corroborated the findings from the performed interview inquiry. During the conversation, how many primary topics emerged?

Institutional Support Gap: Numerous teacher education and study programs on media literacy need more publicly available information resources about the issue, which instructors are encouraged to offer independently. Media competency frequently leads to uneven coverage of various courses.

Acceptance resulted in inconsistency: Certain educators, in his view, trainees, and coworkers occasionally saw media literacy as an essential talent, not only as an "addition" or "supplement," but as integral to "work". Consequently, future educators must integrate media literacy into their educational practices to fully comprehend its significance since more than just understanding is required. This decline in educational quality diminishes young people's access to a comprehensive education.

Media Literacy in Educational Challenges: Teachers' media competency in addressing issues, particularly the media's role in fostering critical thinking and skepticism, is stressed. According to students, their message indicates that public information media often renders consumers inactive, and they encounter vital information online regarding their struggles.

This presents challenges regardless of the extent. Teachers' qualifications are essential for enhancing public information media, and the entrance qualifications for media professionals are being reinforced due to their efforts. Some students employ successful strategies for media literacy activities, including practical research, media projects, and digital narratives they have developed. However, as evidenced, more significant obstacles to success prevent the improvement of media competence through extensive, comprehensive institutional methods.

3. Fundamental Discoveries

There is a disparity in future educators' ability to engage with media content and utilize digital tools effectively and critically. Digital familiarity is high, although the critical appraisal of public information tools and the worrisome moral implications are significant areas of concern.

There is a structural requirement for training: Trainee teachers and the instruction of both students and instructors in media literacy programs necessitate more formal and systematic approaches, as stated.

Educators' training necessitates a cohesive approach to media literacy inside institutions since prospective teachers encounter challenges in their coursework. There is a pressing need to explore alternative solutions and scientific advancements to address these issues effectively.

Discussion

1. Strategies for the educational development of media competency

Teachers' education and credentials enhance courses focused on constructing media competence, emphasizing theoretical and practical components of media literacy, which necessitates a strategic pedagogical approach. The primary objective is for future educators to comprehend the technological aspects of digital media, enabling them to provide their pupils with the critical thinking and ethical tools necessary for development. This approach elucidates the efficacy of various instructional strategies implemented.

Request predicated on education.

Requests for educational initiatives should focus on developing robust strategies for enhancing media competency. This strategy enables students to formulate questions, learn from issues, and engage with media content related to their concepts. A critical study of public information tools, messages, biases, and sources is required for projects presented during the internship.

Media environment for educators: Their understanding can deepen. For instance, educators instructing inside the program may compare students' publications to judge the credibility of sources, which might lead to misconceptions regarding their assignments. Moreover, their analytical abilities improve due to the practical application of public information tools and activities.

To advance project-based media production for release

Practical, project-based instruction for future teachers in media literacy should provide an engaging and productive method. Produce digital media—videos, blogs, podcasts, or infographics—utilizing public information technologies for educators. This involves creating procedures that include ethical commentary and audience engagement while developing credible visual and textual material. Public information technologies facilitate the dissemination of information to prospective educators.

c) Cooperative learning in media literacy within the environment cultivates future educators by collaboratively developing public information tools addressing complicated topics. According to the group projects, media literacy includes students' opinions, the practical research analyses they conduct, and the collective results they produce, all of which encourage critical communication and commentary. Teachers in education can collaboratively instruct activities, utilizing public information resources that depend on the topic of discussion or the conclusions they make, as well as the overall learning culture and diverse perspectives they cultivate.

d) Qualifications for public information tools in an independent course and media literacy integration will enhance the effectiveness of strategies based on educators' training in other scientific disciplines. For instance, media literacy and historical context can enhance students' understanding of current events, including scientific topics such as climate change and pandemics.

2. The impact of social networking environments on media literacy

What is the extent of the research findings for participants in the education sector? Significant consequences are emphasized. Media literacy is a crucial component of contemporary education, necessitating the incorporation of media competency into teacher training programs to effectively facilitate a transformative social vision. In this context, the extent of the offer is:

Entry for Teacher Certification Standards on Media Literacy

The current needs for public information necessitate the integration of teacher qualifications and certification criteria. At that time, several educators in various countries were transferring out of certification for media literacy, as formal training did not mandate this admission for institutions, making it voluntary. The media literacy level of future teachers is constant and will not decline. Media literacy is required for core competence admission requirements in all educational programs. All educators, whether in science or geography, may significantly enhance their media competency levels from a stringent perspective.

Media literacy aligned with training for incentive creation.

Teachers must meet media literacy certification standards, and educational institutions should develop robust media literacy programs. This research examines strategies that facilitate funding, enhance academic credentials, and foster collaboration with media and technology corporations. This initiative aims to enhance educators' media competency through comprehensive initiatives designed to provide essential resources, tools, and training investments, alleviating challenges. Media literacy aligned with the organization's collaborative efforts on the path forward.

Governments and educational institutions frequently collaborate with media literacy groups to provide necessary solutions in this specialized sector. UNESCO advocates for global public information tools and literacy, collaborating with local IT organizations and educational programs to utilize resources, research, and best practices. This partnership enhances media literacy within institutions. Media literacy in school must align with digital equality initiatives.

d) Digital equality solutions are crucial for addressing significant issues. As seen by education students and instructors, media literacy is potentially reinforced; moreover, it needs more specific locations, necessitating the utilization of digital technologies and the Internet. Policy work exists socio-economic or geographical constraints from a specific location. All future instructors and interns must have the digital infrastructure to develop media competency. This service must display regions suitable for large-scale investment, digital device subsidies, and digital literacy initiatives, as each is intended to be independently provided.

3. National Comparison: The Future of Educators in Media Literacy

Various national settings regarding media literacy might provide significant concepts and findings for comparing media competency in different nations' teacher education systems. While media literacy education is a growing and vital area of focus in some countries, it is a well-established part of curricula in others.

Finland model

Finland frequently exemplifies good integration in media literacy education, particularly in language acquisition. Finnish schools emphasize critical thinking and media literacy from an early age, with a dedicated emphasis on these areas, also reflected in their educational style. In Finland, prospective educators are instructed to use digital tools and critically evaluate public information resources for teaching pupils. Media literacy seems to be a fundamental ability for democratic participation, and the Finnish government actively supports projects to enhance media competence within society.

Health Literacy among American Joint States Educators

Historically, media literacy in the United States is linked to fragmented elements in Rhode Island. Media education in university laboratories, particularly in innovation, is only sometimes integrated into all teacher education programs despite the importance of media literacy. According to the organization National Priority Direction for Media Literacy, educators in education rotate for more policy support requested. However, the unequal advancement of publicly available information indicates that the certification to teach remains a significant duty. Yet, it still separates instructors and schools, leading to a decline in performance.

Enhancing a nation's media literacy

Although media literacy is still a young field, the economy is changing despite these obstacles: poor educational integration, inadequate infrastructure, a lack of funding, and digital disparities. The significance of media literacy understanding is recognized in India, particularly in South Africa. Teacher training programs often emphasize critical media literacy alongside fundamental computer abilities, warranting further attention. Public efforts and non-governmental and non-profit organizations need to be more adequately given media literacy training to teachers and students in these areas, aiming to facilitate knowledge transmission through various channels.

d) National Comparative Analysis Insights

This international comparison demonstrates media literacy. The globe is acknowledged on a spectrum; its integration of instructors into education is quite diversified. Finland employs an

active governmental strategy, serving as a good model for other countries. The primary takeaway from this comparison is that media literacy is not only technical talent but an essential component of citizenship education that requires integration at all educational levels, along with necessary legislative support and help.

4. Educators' credentials in media literacy for the future

The digital world is developing, and educators must enhance media literacy in education since comprehensive instruction requires great current relevance. Artificial intelligence (AI), augmented reality (AR), and deepfake technologies contribute to a burgeoning issue in media literacy as they increasingly blur the line between truth and falsehood, complicating the discernment of reality. Future educators must not only master this technology themselves but also prepare pupils to navigate the complexities of public information tools critically.

a) Artificial Intelligence and Media Literacy

The release of media output and the advancement of artificial intelligence will significantly impact media literacy in the next few years, addressing critical issues. Artificial intelligence systems are increasingly curating individualized news material for individuals based on their social media feeds. Educators require training to effectively teach students about the impact of artificial intelligence on media consumption, fostering a critical understanding of algorithm-based public information tools. This excerpt addresses the moral implications of AI for future educators, including data privacy, algorithmic prejudice, AI-generated material's impact on public discourse, and the necessary equipment for such discussions.

b) Deepfake and erroneous data

Deepfake technology, utilizing artificial intelligence for manipulation, generates videos and images that mislead viewers online. This capability poses a significant threat, as it creates highly realistic yet fabricated media content. While it offers opportunities, it can also facilitate the dissemination of misinformation and manipulate public opinion. Educators in the educational program for prospective teachers must discern the implications of deepfake technology and its impact on instructing and assessing pupils, particularly on the availability of public information.

c) Digital literacy training should be lifelong since the rapidly evolving digital ecosystem needs ongoing education for instructors. More than initial training is required and restrictive. Recent media and technology trends significantly inform teachers' continuous professional growth. Teachers' engagement in media literacy is essential for effective instruction in school education. To reach this goal, continuous professional development through seminars, conferences, and online courses is necessary.

Recognitions

We want to stress the surveys and talks attended by students and instructors from this excerpt. Their own experiences and thoughts will be shared to assess the preparedness of this research, which aims to enhance opportunities and their contributions and provide essential information.

Conclusions

This research highlights the increasing significance of media competency in education, underscoring the future role of instructors in mastering digital technologies and fostering comparable abilities in students to evaluate public information resources critically. Digital public information technologies are increasingly significant in both personal and professional domains,

particularly for educators and students. However, the prevalence of inaccurate data in management necessitates proper training and resources.

This study's results indicate that many digital literacy teachers possess a functional degree of media material critical assessment and abilities of responsible use, although in a large capacity. Educational institutions face more significant challenges in effectively integrating media literacy programs into their curricula. Discussion of fundamental pedagogical strategies, including survey-based education, project-based media creation, and interdisciplinary integration, enhances teacher qualifications and improves media competency in program development. This research highlights the significance of media literacy in teacher certification requirements, emphasizing the necessity of training and organizational collaboration, including governmental interventions. International comparisons indicate that Finland effectively integrates media literacy into schools, exemplifying a successful method that enhances public information services and is a good model for other countries. The developing economy faces unique challenges; nonetheless, public efforts and international collaboration in media literacy on a global scale enhance its potential.

Future media literacy training for educators must adapt to rapid technological advancements, including AI, deepfake technologies, and the proliferation of algorithm-driven disinformation. Teachers' continuously increasing digital media competency is essential for continued professional growth in the landscape of competent teaching. A summary of the teacher's media competency in educational integration is essential and potentially pertinent. Digital media community information must persist as a public information tool essential for equipping future generations with fundamental skills. Teachers facilitate the development of students' media literacy by providing tools and information, enabling young individuals to become aware, responsible, and active participants in the digital world.

REFERENCES

1. Alfredo, R., Echeverria, V., Jin, Y., Yan, L., Swiecki, Z., Gašević, D., & Martinez-Maldonado, R. (2024). Human-Centred Learning Analytics and AI in Education: a Systematic Literature Review. *Computers and Education Artificial Intelligence*, 100215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2024.100215>
2. Anusca, F. (2013). DIGCOMP: A framework for developing and understanding digital competence in Europe. *E-learning Papers*, 38, 1. <https://doi.org/10.2788/52966>
3. Baldiņš, A. (2016). Insights into e-pedagogy Concept Development. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 231, 251–255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.09.099>
4. Buckingham, D. (2022). Media education and citizenship in neoliberal times. In *Routledge eBooks* (pp. 83–90). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003175599-13>
5. Çebi, A., Özdemir, T. B., Reisoğlu, İ., & Çolak, C. (2022). From digital competences to technology integration: Re-formation of pre-service teachers' knowledge and understanding. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 113, 101965. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2022.101965>
6. Chiu, T. K., Ahmad, Z., Ismailov, M., & Sanusi, I. T. (2024). What are Artificial Intelligence Literacy and Competency for non-engineering? A Comprehensive Framework to Support Them. *Computers and Education Open*, 100171. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeo.2024.100171>

7. Dang, T. D., Phan, T. T., Vu, T. N. Q., La, T. D., & Pham, V. K. (2024). Digital competence of lecturers and its impact on student learning value in higher education. *Heliyon*, 10(17), e37318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e37318>
8. Ferrari, A. (2012). Digital Competence in Practice: An Analysis of Frameworks Publications Office of the European. (n.d.). *Publications Office of the European Union*. [10.2791/82116](https://doi.org/10.2791/82116)
9. Estaji, M., Banitalebi, Z., & Brown, G. T. (2024). The key competencies and components of teacher assessment literacy in digital environments: A scoping review. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 141, 104497. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2024.104497>
10. Galindo-Domínguez, H., Delgado, N., Campo, L., & Losada, D. (2024). Relationship between teachers' digital competence and attitudes towards artificial intelligence in education. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 126, 102381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2024.102381>
11. Gu, M. M., Huang, C. F., & Lee, C. J. (2023). Investigating university students' digital citizenship development through the lens of digital literacy practice: A Translingual and transemiotizing perspective. *Linguistics and Education*, 77, 101226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.linged.2023.101226>
12. Hatlevik, O. E., & Christophersen, K. (2012). Digital competence at the beginning of upper secondary school: Identifying factors explaining digital inclusion. *Computers & Education*, 63, 240–247. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2012.11.015>
13. Hobbs, R. (2017). Measuring the digital and media literacy competencies of children and teens. In *Elsevier eBooks* (pp. 253–274). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-809481-5.00013-4>
14. Jenkins, H. (2007). The work of Theory in the age of digital Transformation. *A Companion to Film Theory*, December 10, 234–261. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470998410.ch14>
15. Kärkkäinen, K., Jääskelä, P., & Tynjälä, P. (2023). How does university teachers' pedagogical training meet topical challenges raised by educational research? A case study from Finland. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 128, 104088. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2023.104088>
16. Kiryakova, A., Olkhovaya, T., & Rodionova, T. (2015). Axiological foundations of Media Education in Modern University. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 214, 143–149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.11.606>
17. Koshanova, M. T., Abdirkenova, A. K., Seiitkazy, P. B., Koshanova, Z. T., & Seitkassymov, A. A. (2021). The use of media technologies in the formation of creativity in future psychological and pedagogical specialists. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 41, 100891. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2021.100891>
18. Kress, M., Gordonov, A., Blank, A., & Moroh, M. (1997). ComWeb: An electronic classroom for teaching computer literacy. *Computers & Education*, 29(4), 181–187. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0360-1315\(97\)00035-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0360-1315(97)00035-3)
19. Kruskopf, M., Abdulhamed, R., Ranta, M., Lammassaari, H., & Lonka, K. (2024). Future teachers' self-efficacy in teaching practical and algorithmic ICT competencies – Does background matter? *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 144, 104574. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2024.104574>
20. Mirzagitova, A., Mukhametgaliyeva, S., & Tirigulova, R. (2015). Realization of competence-based approach in preparation of the competitive specialist. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 191, 1938–1940. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.04.288>

21. Nagel, I., Guðmundsdóttir, G. B., & Afdal, H. W. (2023). Teacher educators' professional agency in facilitating professional digital competence. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 132, 104238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2023.104238>
22. Navío-Marco, J., Mendieta-Aragón, A., De Tejada Muñoz, V. F., & Ruiz, M. J. B. (2024). Driving students' engagement and satisfaction in blended and online learning universities: Use of learner-generated media in business management subjects. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 22(2), 100963. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2024.100963>
23. O'Bannon, B. W., & Thomas, K. M. (2015). Mobile phones in the classroom: Preservice teachers answer the call. *Computers & Education*, 85, 110–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2015.02.010>
24. Sanchez, G., & Jenkins, J. H. (2024). Social media & subjectivity: Adolescent lived experiences with social media in a Southern California middle school. *Social Science & Medicine*, 348, 116839. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2024.116839>
25. Scherer, R., Tondeur, J., & Siddiq, F. (2017). On the quest for validity: Testing the factor structure and measurement invariance of the technology-dimensions in the Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) model. *Computers & Education*, 112, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2017.04.012>
26. Schmitz, M., Consoli, T., Antonietti, C., Cattaneo, A., Gonon, P., & Petko, D. (2023). Why do some teachers teach media literacy while others do not? Exploring predictors along the “will, skill, tool, pedagogy” model. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 151, 108004. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2023.108004>
27. Svensson, M., & Baelo, R. (2015). Teacher Students' Perceptions of their Digital Competence. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 180, 1527–1534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.02.302>
28. Timm, S., Kaukko, M., & Scheunpflug, A. (2023). Preservice teachers' professional beliefs in relation to global social change: Findings from Finland and Germany. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 132, 104239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2023.104239>
29. Tomczyk, Ł. (2024). Digital competence among pre-service teachers: A global perspective on curriculum change as viewed by experts from 33 countries. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 105, 102449. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evalprogplan.2024.102449>
30. Tømte, C. E., Pedersen, C., Vennerød-Diesen, F. F., & Daus, S. (2023). Early and late adopter effects between schools in a one-to-one computer initiative. *Computers & Education*, 207, 104927. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2023.104927>
31. Tømte, C., Enochsson, A., Buskqvist, U., & Kårstein, A. (2015). Educating online student teachers to master professional digital competence: The TPACK-framework goes online. *Computers & Education*, 84, 26–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2015.01.005>
32. Wang, Y., Chen, Y., & Benitez-Amado, J. (2014). How information technology influences environmental performance: Empirical evidence from China. *International Journal of Information Management*, 35(2), 160–170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2014.11.005>
33. Yu, H. (2024). The application and challenges of ChatGPT in educational transformation: New demands for teachers' roles. *Heliyon*, 10(2), e24289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e24289>